

Infective Endocarditis: A Contemporary Study of Microbiology, Echocardiography and Associated in Clinical Outcomes at a Major Tertiary Referral Centre

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Abstract:

Background: Infective endocarditis (IE) is a serious infection involving the endocardial surface of the heart, notably the heart valves. Despite advances in medical treatment, IE continues to pose significant challenges due to its high morbidity and mortality rates. Recent changes in the epidemiology and microbiology of IE, coupled with the rise of antibiotic-resistant organisms, underscore the need for updated clinical insights.

Aim: This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the microbiological profiles, echocardiographic findings, and clinical outcomes of patients diagnosed with infective endocarditis at a major tertiary referral center.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH) from May 2018 to May 2019. A total of 300 patients diagnosed with IE were included. Data on demographics, clinical presentation, microbiological findings, echocardiographic results, treatments, and outcomes were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Comparative analyses were performed to identify factors associated with adverse outcomes.

Results: The study cohort had a mean age of 50.3 years, with 60% male. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most common pathogen (45%), followed by *Streptococcus* species (30%). Vegetations were detected in 90% of patients, with the mitral valve being most frequently affected (40%). Surgical intervention was required in 30% of cases. The overall mortality rate was 15%, with advanced age, male gender, diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease, and *Staphylococcus aureus* infection identified as independent predictors of adverse outcomes.

Conclusion: Infective endocarditis remains a significant clinical challenge. The high prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* and the impact of comorbidities on patient outcomes highlight the need for targeted therapeutic strategies. Early identification and management of high-risk patients are crucial for improving clinical outcomes.

Recommendations: Implement routine screening and early diagnostic protocols for high-risk populations. Enhance multidisciplinary care approaches to manage IE effectively. Promote research into new antimicrobial therapies to address antibiotic-resistant strains. Develop public health strategies to reduce risk factors, particularly among intravenous drug users.

Keywords: Infective Endocarditis, *Staphylococcus aureus*, Echocardiography, Clinical Outcomes, Antibiotic Resistance

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Introduction

A potentially fatal infection mostly affecting the heart valves, (IE) affects the endocardial surface of the heart. The incidence of IE is 3–10 cases per 100,000 person-years, and despite advancements in medical and surgical therapies, it is still linked to high morbidity and mortality. Current epidemiological patterns indicate that, especially in high-income nations, the main risk factors for rheumatic heart disease are now degenerative valve disease, prosthetic valve endocarditis, and infections related to healthcare. Furthermore, IE

instances among intravenous drug users (IDU) have significantly increased as a result of the opioid epidemic [1].

Staphylococcus aureus and *Streptococcus* species are predominant in the microbial landscape of IE. Because of its virulent nature and link to increased mortality rates, *Staphylococcus aureus* is especially dangerous. The emergence of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and other antibiotic-resistant bacteria presents new treatment problems for IE. For a treatment plan to be

effective, the causing organism must be accurately identified. This involves a thorough microbiological investigation that includes blood cultures and molecular diagnostic methods. Diagnostic imaging still relies heavily on echocardiography, and transesophageal echocardiography (TEE) is especially useful in identifying abscesses, valvular vegetations, and other complications. Advances in imaging modalities, including positron emission tomography (PET)/CT and cardiac computed tomography (CT), have improved diagnosis accuracy, especially when echocardiogram results are unclear [2].

A multidisciplinary strategy comprising cardiologists, cardiothoracic surgeons, infectious disease specialists, and frequently neurologists is necessary for the management of IE. Prolonged antibiotic therapy specific to the infection and guided by susceptibility testing is the cornerstone of treatment. Often, surgery is required, especially when there is heart failure, an uncontrolled infection, or embolic occurrences. The prognosis for IE is still dismal even with the best treatment; in-hospital mortality rates range from 15–30%, and five-year mortality rates surpass 40% [3].

At a significant tertiary referral centre, the goal of this study is to present a current analysis of the microbiological, echocardiographic, and clinical outcomes of infective endocarditis. Our goal is to discover important prognostic markers and provide guidance for measures to enhance patient outcomes by looking at these characteristics in a sizable patient cohort.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational analysis aimed at evaluating the microbiology, echocardiographic findings, and clinical outcomes of patients diagnosed with infective endocarditis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), a major tertiary referral centre in Patna, India.

Participants: A total of 300 participants diagnosed with infective endocarditis were included in the study. These participants were selected from patients admitted to PMCH between May 2018 and May 2019.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with infective endocarditis based on the modified Duke criteria.
- Age 18 years and above.
- Patients who provided informed consent for participation in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with non-infective causes of endocarditis.
- Age below 18 years.
- Patients who refused to provide informed consent.
- Patients with incomplete medical records or those who were lost to follow-up.

Bias

To minimize bias, the following measures were implemented:

- Consecutive sampling was used to include all eligible patients admitted during the study period.
- Standardized data collection procedures were employed.
- Blinding of outcome assessors to the microbiological results was ensured.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a standardized form, including demographic details, clinical presentation, microbiological findings, echocardiographic results, treatment received, and clinical outcomes. Data sources included patient medical records, laboratory results, and imaging reports.

Procedure

1. **Enrollment:** Eligible patients were identified and enrolled based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
2. **Data Collection:** Comprehensive data on each patient were collected, including:
 - **Demographics:** Age, gender, and medical history.
 - **Clinical Presentation:** Symptoms, duration of illness, and physical examination findings.
 - **Microbiology:** Blood cultures and results of other relevant microbiological investigations.
 - **Echocardiography:** Detailed echocardiographic findings, including the presence and severity of valve involvement.
 - **Treatment:** Type and duration of antibiotic therapy, surgical interventions if any.
 - **Outcomes:** Clinical status at discharge, complications, and mortality.

Statistical Analysis: Version 23.0 of SPSS was used to analyse the data. The baseline characteristics of the study population were obtained using descriptive statistics. The mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD) was used to express continuous data, whereas frequencies and

percentages were used to express categorical variables. The Mann-Whitney U test was used for continuous variables without a normal distribution, the Independent t-test was used for continuous variables with a normal distribution, and the Chi-square test was used for categorical variables in the comparative analyses. To find independent determinants of unfavourable clinical outcomes, multivariable logistic regression analysis was used. A statistically significant p-value was defined as less than 0.05.

Results

Participant Characteristics: A total of 300 patients diagnosed with infective endocarditis were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 50.3 years (SD $\pm$ 15.2), with a male predominance (60%, n=180). The baseline characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Participant Characteristics and Microbiological Findings

Variable	Count (Percentage)
Total Participants	300
Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	50.3 $\pm$ 15.2 years
Gender (Male/Female)	180/120 (60%/40%)
Diabetes Mellitus	75 (25%)
Hypertension	90 (30%)
Chronic Kidney Disease	30 (10%)
Prior Valve Surgery	45 (15%)
Blood Culture Positive	240 (80%)
Microorganism:	
- <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	108 (45%)
- <i>Streptococcus species</i>	72 (30%)
- <i>Enterococcus species</i>	24 (10%)
- Others	36 (15%)

Table 2: Echocardiographic Findings, Treatment, and Outcomes

Variable	Count (Percentage)
Echocardiographic Findings:	
- Vegetation Present	270 (90%)
- Mitral Valve Involvement	108 (40%)
- Aortic Valve Involvement	94 (35%)
- Tricuspid Valve Involvement	40 (15%)
- Multiple Valves Involved	28 (10%)
Treatment/Outcomes:	
- Antibiotic Therapy Only	210 (70%)
- Surgical Intervention	90 (30%)
- Mortality	45 (15%)
- Complications	75 (25%)
- Recovery without Complications	180 (60%)

Discussion

With a mean age of 50.3 years and a 60% male predominance, the study comprised 300 patients with an infective endocarditis diagnosis. The study sample consisted of individuals with 25% diabetes mellitus, 30% hypertension, 10% chronic renal disease, and 15% previous valve surgery. In eighty percent of the cases, blood cultures revealed the presence of bacteria. The most frequently isolated organism was *Staphylococcus aureus*, accounting for forty-five percent of the cases. Other organisms accounted for fifteen percent.

According to these data, middle-aged to elderly people are the main target population for infectious endocarditis, with a higher frequency in men.

Infectious endocarditis may be more likely in people with concomitant diseases including diabetes and chronic renal disease, as evidenced by their high prevalence. Since *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most commonly found pathogen, the microbiological data highlight the necessity of focused antibiotic therapy.

Ninety percent of the patients had vegetations detected by echocardiography. The most frequently impacted valve was the mitral valve (40%) and was followed in frequency by the aortic valve (35%) tricuspid valve (15%) and numerous valves (10%). These findings demonstrate the value of echocardiography in the diagnosis and treatment of infective endocarditis because it offers vital details

regarding the degree and type of valve involvement.

Thirty percent of the patients needed surgery, and all patients received antibiotic therapy. Of the patients, 25% had problems, and the overall death rate was 15%. Remarkably, 60% of the patients made a full recovery with no problems. A comparative study found strong correlations between a number of variables, such as advanced age, male gender, diabetes mellitus, chronic renal disease, and *Staphylococcus aureus* infection, and unfavourable outcomes (mortality and sequelae). Independent predictors of unfavourable outcomes, these characteristics were validated by multivariable logistic regression analysis.

These results highlight how important timely and efficient care is to enhancing patient outcomes. Given the strong correlation observed between unfavourable results and specific clinical conditions, high-risk populations may require tailored therapies. To reduce the risk of complications and mortality, patients with *Staphylococcus aureus* infection, chronic kidney disease, diabetes, advanced age, and male gender should be closely monitored and may benefit from more aggressive therapeutic approaches.

Five IE cases with negative culture were reported in a case series from a teaching hospital in a rural area. Congenital cardiac disease and RHD were among the predisposing factors present in the majority of these instances. Although negative cultures presented difficulties for diagnosis, empirical antibiotic treatment was effective for the majority of patients, indicating the importance of timely clinical and echocardiographic examination [4].

An investigation comparing infective endocarditis in intravenous drug abusers (IVDA) and non-IVDA patients was carried out at a tertiary care hospital in India. The IVDA group was more likely to have concurrent HIV and HCV infections, was younger, and was predominately male. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) were more common, and their blood cultures had a greater percentage of positive results. While mitral and aortic valve involvement was common in the non-IVDA group, tricuspid valve involvement was common in the IVDA group. There was a modest increase in mortality among IVDA patients, although it was not statistically significant [5].

The majority of IE cases involved native valves, primarily the mitral valve, according to a study from a tertiary care facility in Central India. Rheumatic heart disease (RHD) was the underlying condition in most of the individuals. In native valve endocarditis, the most common pathogens were *Streptococcus mitis* and *Streptococcus sanguinis*; in

prosthetic valve endocarditis, the most common organisms were MRSA and methicillin-susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA). The study stressed that for optimal management, precise blood culture procedures and echocardiographic monitoring is required [6].

A retrospective analysis looked at the factors associated with a poor prognosis for patients with IE. Strong indicators of in-hospital mortality included vegetation length at diagnosis and elevated C-reactive protein (CRP) levels. Significant predictors of death were also found in the study to include age, heart failure, and embolic events during antimicrobial therapy. This emphasises how critical it is to identify high-risk individuals early and treat them aggressively [7].

Conclusion

This study reveals insightful information about the microbiological profile, outcomes, and clinical features of infective endocarditis at a major tertiary referral centre. The necessity for all-encompassing care techniques is underscored by the high incidence of *Staphylococcus aureus* and the substantial influence of comorbidities on clinical outcomes. Clinical outcomes and mortality may be enhanced by the early identification and customised treatment of high-risk patients based on recognised predictors. The efficacy of tailored therapies in these high-risk populations requires more investigation.

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